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(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted-phenyl) [(substituted-phenyl)azo]methylene]hydrazides as Possible Anthelmintics

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A number of compounds with benzothiazole as parent nucleus are known to possess various biological activities including anthelmintic activity¹. Recently, hydrazides² and azo compounds³ have also been used in the therapy of helminthiasis. These observations prompted us to synthesise the title compounds as per Scheme 1 with a view to evaluate their anthelmintic efficacy.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid hydrazide: It was prepared according to the reported procedure⁴.

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazides: These compounds were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of (2-benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid hydrazide and substituted-benzaldehyde in methanol for 5 h. The solid separated was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no **	R ₁	R ₂	M p °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1. ^a	NO ₂	H	166	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
2. ^b	OH	OCH ₃	108	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
3.	H	Cl	122	77	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl

*N analysis found satisfactory for all compounds
**ν_{max} ^a3 420 (NH), 1 680 (amide C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 530 (NO₂); ^b3 420 (NH), 1 680 (amide C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH).

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	NO ₂	H	4-Cl	146	84	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
2.	NO ₂	H	3-NO ₂	150	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
3.	NO ₂	H	4-NO ₂	153	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
4.	NO ₂	H	4-COOH	148	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
5.	NO ₂	H	4-CH ₃	147	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂
6. ^a	NO ₂	H	4-OH	151	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
7.	OH	OCH ₃	4-Cl	102	81	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Cl
8.	OH	OCH ₃	3-NO ₂	98	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
9. ^b	OH	OCH ₃	4-NO ₂	65	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
10.	OH	OCH ₃	4-COOH	95	67	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₆ S ₂
11.	OH	OCH ₃	4-CH ₃	108	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂
12.	OH	OCH ₃	4 OH	116	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂
13.	H	Cl	3-NO ₂	78	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
14.	H	Cl	4-Cl	140	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl ₂
15.	H	Cl	4-COOH	137	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
16.	H	Cl	2-OH	138	81	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
17.	H	Cl	4-NO ₂	135	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ S ₂ Cl
18.	H	Cl	4-CH ₃	134	61	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS ₂ Cl

*N analysis found satisfactory for all the compounds; Compounds sl nos. 2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 15, 16 and 17 screened for anthelmintic activity. **ν_{max} ^a1 680 (CO), 3 500 (OH), 1 610 (N=N) and 1 530 (NO₂); ^b1 680 (CO), 3 420 (NH), 1 610 (N=N) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid [(substituted-phenyl) [(substituted-phenyl)azo]methylene]hydrazides: To sodium nitrite (0.02 mol) dissolved in water and cooled to 0°, was added to an ice-cold solution of an aromatic amine (0.015 mol) in concentrated HCl. The mixture was poured into a cold solution of (2-benzothiazolylthio)acetic acid

[(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazide (0.01 mol) dissolved in pyridine. The resulting coloured solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

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Synthesis of 3-[4-(4'-Oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole and its Diarylidene Derivatives

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ALTHOUGH the synthesis and biological activities¹ of thiazolidinone derivatives have been studied by several investigators, compounds containing two thiazolidinone moieties, one fused to a triazole ring and the other in the form of a side chain are not known. In continuation of our earlier work² of this series we report here the synthesis of compound 4 starting from *p*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (1) which was obtained from *p*-aminobenzoic acid by standard procedure³.

The hydrazine (1) gave 1-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)-thiosemicarbazide (2) after reacting with potassium thiocyanate in concentrated HCl. The thiosemicarbazide, when heated with 10% KOH, furnished

5-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)-2-mercapto-*s*-triazole (3) as crystalline solid. Condensation of 3 with monochloroacetic acid and NaOAc in absolute ethanol gave 3-[4-(4'-oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-*a*]triazole (4). The diarylidene derivatives (5) were synthesised from 4 by reacting with aromatic aldehydes in acetic acid and sodium acetate (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The ir spectra of 2 showed a strong carbonyl band at 1 720 cm^{-1} and two broad bands at 3 500–3 150 cm^{-1} corresponding to primary and secondary amino functions. Its cyclised product triazole (3) did not show any carbonyl absorption but a weak band at 2 420 cm^{-1} corresponding to SH confirmed the structure. The thiazolidinone (4) showed two carbonyl absorptions at 1 745 and 1 720 cm^{-1} and the other band at 2 955 cm^{-1} (CH_2). The dibenzylidene derivative (5; $\text{Ar}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) of 4 gave carbonyl absorptions at 1 730 and 1 700 cm^{-1} and the band at 2 955 cm^{-1} was absent. The bathochromic shifts of the carbonyls are due to their conjugation with the oxocyclic double bond.

Experimental

All melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

1-(4-Thioureidobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide (2): A mixture of *p*-aminobenzoyl hydrazine (1.5 g, 10 mmol), potassium thiocyanate (4 g, 40 mmol), concentrated HCl (10 ml) and water (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After cooling, the resulting yellow solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (1.57 g, 60%), m p. 200° (Found . S, 23.60 $\text{C}_9\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{OH}_{1.1}$ requires : S, 23.79%); ν_{max} 3 500–3 150br (NH, NH_2), 1 680 (C=O), 1 610, 1 590 and 1 440 cm^{-1} .

5-(4-Thioureido)phenyl-2-mercapto-*s*-triazole (3): A mixture of 1-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide (2.7 g, 10 mmol) and 10% KOH solution (30 ml) was refluxed slowly over direct flame for 3 h. The